

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B338
Date: 17 January 2008
Take Off: 08:45:51Z
Landing: 14:22:17Z
Flight Time: 5h36m26

Campaign: APPRAISE Clouds

Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM2	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics Training	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8	Chemistry & TDLAS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	CVI Training	Rob King	Met Office
10	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office
11	CPI	Hazel Jones	University of Manchester
12	CPI Training	Chris Deardon	University of Manchester
13	AMS	Jonny Crosier	University of Manchester
14	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM

Flight Track:

B338 Track 17-JAN-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B338
 Date: 17 Jan 2008
 Project: APPRAISE Clouds
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
073530		Start-Up	0.69 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W
084551		T/O	2.9 kft	292	Cranfield
090033		Video	10.0 kft	243	Start FFC & UFC1
090141		Event	10.0 kft	243	JW & Nevz zero
091053		Event	10.0 kft	175	Heimann cal test
091745	093138	Profile 1	10.0 - 24.0 kft	226	1000fpm
093357	094254	Run 1	24.0 kft	092	Eastbound
094829	100220	Run 2	22.1 - 22.0 kft	260	Westbound
095128		Event	22.0 kft	258	Heimann cal test
100427	101415	Run 3	20.0 kft	085	Eastbound
101937	103514	Run 4	18.0 kft	259	Westbound
103325		Video	18.1 kft	252	Start FFC & UFC2
103709		Event	16.2 kft	074	Zero JW
103724	104537	Run 5	16.0 - 16.1 kft	080	Eastbound
104706	110242	Run 5.2	16.1 - 16.0 kft	258	West bound
105654		Event	16.0 kft	250	Heimann cal
110439	111553	Run 6	14.1 - 14.0 kft	069	Eastbound
111907	113548	Profile 2	14.0 - 31.0 kft	251	>1000fpm
113734	114400	Run 7	31.1 - 31.0 kft	070	Above cloud
114316		Event	31.1 kft	051	Contrailing, on RFC
114551	115950	Run 7.2	31.1 - 31.0 kft	261	Westbound
114709		Event	31.1 kft	266	Zero JW & Nevz
120340	121023	Run 8	26.1 kft	065	In cloud top
120621		Video	26.1 kft	069	Start FFC & UFC3
121345	123155	Run 9	24.0 kft	263	Westbound
123412	124315	Run 10	21.1 kft	061	Eastbound, in cloud
123544		Event	21.1 kft	069	Zero JW & Nevz
124839	130547	Run 11	18.0 kft	258	Westbound
130414		Event	18.0 kft	257	Tornado Intercept
130754	131658	Run 12	15.0 - 15.1 kft	057	Eastbound
131823	133838	Run 12.2	15.0 kft	269	Westbound
131942		Event	15.0 kft	265	Zero JW & Nevz
133306		Event	15.0 kft	250	Heimann cal
133917		Video	15.1 kft	295	Start FFC & UFC4
134148	134945	Run 13	12.1 kft	081	Eastbound
140128		ASP	10.0 kft	341	Close
142217		Land	0.92 kft	355	Cranfield
142829		Shutdown	0.91 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MS INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B338 Track 17-JAN-08

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Ice: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 17 Jan 2008

Flight Number: B338

TO time: 09.00z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal altocumulus clouds in association with Chilbolton radar.

Sortie Location: Area Alpha. Over and to the west of Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base, within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. In this case, the aircraft may fly a small butterfly pattern in which only one of the legs is parallel to the wind direction or radar azimuth. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles. On occasion, the aircraft flight legs may start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so will limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area west of Chilbolton.
- b) T+35 When in a suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions (This may best be achieved with an approach to Boscombe Down airfield). Fly leg in **clear air** for 10 min.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above mid level cloud top, whichever is lower (40min)
- d) Establish start/end points of 40-60km of level flight legs along the azimuth which is being scanned by the radar. Fly these legs at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, in middle of cloud, just below cloud top and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~ 5-10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs Mission Scientist will request AMS and UHSAS to switch to sample off CVI inlet - but sample off Rosemount inlets out of cloud. Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min).

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Ice – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, SID-2 and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI and 2DS (when available) – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, WCPC, UHSAS (- ability to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)
- Filters

Inlets: CVI inlet will be required for sampling of incloud residuals by AMS & UHSAS

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Ice: mixed-phase cloud studies
Flight Number: B338, 17 Jan 2008
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Weather conditions & Aims:

An occluded front crossed W to E over the whole of southern England between 6am and 1pm. The purpose of this flight was to examine the ice and liquid phase microphysical processes of the mid level clouds associated with this system whilst it was being remotely sensed by the Chilbolton radar/lidar facility. During the period of the flight (09:00 – 14:00) the main areas of precipitation associated with system were forecast (by the MetOffice mesoscale model, 00z run) to be to the east of Chilbolton and the area of operation.

Area of operation:

Southern UK in the area of the Chilbolton radar facility and on a radial to the WSW of Chilbolton avoiding airlines and danger areas.

Summary of the flight:

Transit was at FL100 to the Chilbolton area and was at or just above CT, where the temperature was around -3.8 to -4 degC. Radsearch reported lower level cloud (<2km)

and another cloud layer between 6 and 9-10km (although earlier they had seen supercooled layers around 4km). In theatre, a profile was carried out on the radial from Chilbolton to the WSW, from FL100-FL240. A few cloud particles were observed by CPI and core cloud from around FL160 and above. At FL190 thicker cloud was encountered and both dry and dewpoint temperatures were around -26deg. Aerosol instrumentation (AMS, WCPC and UHSAS) was switched to the CVI inlet at FL220.

A series of straight and level runs (SLRs) were then carried out on the radial back to and from Chilbolton at 2000ft intervals between FL240 and FL140. At FL240 the CPI reported bullet rosettes, plates and aggregates of these and/or chunks of larger ice. CPCs recorded around 400 or 600 particles (cm⁻³ on the CVI inlet). Radsearch reported CB at around 5km (FL164). The 2DS went down during P1 at FL220, and during R1 the 2DP was reported as being very noisy and turned off. On R2 at FL220 a pocket of clear air was encountered, the CVI CPC counts dropped to zero while the water CPC still recorded 200/cm³. Core cloud reported being in and out of cloud, while CPI reported only big ice in cloud. The AMS was not seeing any significant loadings of any species. During R3 (FL200) the AMS CPC was seeing 100-200 cm⁻³, while the CVI CPC was seeing large numbers of particles 1000cm⁻³, and at the same time AMS was seeing organics typical of plastics (Q are these particles being chipped off the CVI inlet by the ice – they go away out of cloud ie the WCPC counts go to zero?). The start of R4 (FL180) overhead Chilbolton was in cloud, but pockets of clear air were encountered. The end of the run (to the SW) was in clear air and aerosol instrumentation was switched to sampling off Rosemount inlets half way through the run. R5 (FL160) ran into cloud only at the end over Chilbolton (aerosol racks were switched to CVI and filters were switched off). Radsearch reported fall streaks to 4km from clouds with bases at 5km. R5.2 was also carried out at FL160 to try to sample these features, but after 2mins only clear air was sampled so filters were switched on and aerosol instruments returned to sample off Rosemount inlets. Towards the end of R5.2 a CVI clear air calibration was carried out (aerosol instruments briefly switched to CVI). R6 inbound to Chilbolton was a below cloud aerosol sampling leg.

Profile P2 between FL140 and FL310 was carried out on the radial away from Chilbolton. After 1min 45s cloud was encountered and filters were switched off and aerosol instruments returned to sample off the CVI inlet. At FL263 a clear air slot was encountered, and the profile became increasingly cloud free with altitude up to FL310. SLRs were then carried out at FL310 (R7, R7.2), FL260 (R8), FL240 (R9), FL210 (R10), FL180 (R11), FL150 (R12, R12.2) and FL120 (R13). R7 and R7.2 were just above CT. Towards the end of R7 we flew below a contrail and we were also generating contrails. The CVI calibration was checked near the end of R7.2. At this stage CT was dropping rapidly, so R8 (inbound) was carried out at FL260 to attempt to fly in cloud. Cloud was encountered soon after the start, and filters turned off and aerosol instruments returned to the CVI inlet. R9 (FL240) was incloud overhead Chilbolton but was in and out of cloud (near CT) throughout the run. Inbound R10 (FL210) was at or above CT much of the time but ran into cloud overhead Chilbolton. R11 (FL180) was in cloud but this was thin at times (could see out of cloud above, below and to the sides in places). This cloud contained much more liquid water (the CPI was seeing drops) and icing was reported (at -

24degC). At the end, R11 was out of most cloud, which was observed to be just a very thin layer at this stage. R12 (FL150) was cloud free, and all clouds at the mid and higher levels had now (13:07) burned off or moved away (as indicated by the radar time series below).

Notes on instrumentation:

The filter system worked better today. The water CPC had problems early on but these were resolved within 30mins. As on previous flights, the 2DS worked up to the point it became too cold, as did 2DP which was then turned off. However the 2DC worked well, as did the CPI and UHSAS. SID1 was fine too while FFSSP was reported to have been “wobbly” at times. The turbulence measurements were better than on previous flights (in the absence of significant supercooled water), while Total water was fine except at the coldest temperatures where the heaters were unable to cope (as expected). Core chemistry instruments had no problems, except a loose pipe was detected early on which was then fixed.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

APPRAISE-ICE

Flight No **B.338** Date **17/01/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **1** of

KNB

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:10	Chilbolton Radar				< 2km S-9km → 6-9km but 5km
8:45:54					Rolling 1000ft
8:46:02					T/O
		1000			CR 1000
		4000			hold to right -
					Gap in cloud - pass missed CT
8:50:13	KNB =	8:50:00			
					Maybe into cloud 7500'
08:56:05	Transit	10000			At CT or just above
					RADSENSEN:-
					light ppt @ lower level Lwd cloud < 2km
					Breaky then 6-9-10 km - higher-level vci cloud
					(Supercooled layers 4km each or in names)
09:12:06		FL00			3 miles NW in 5 mins
09:16:10					CPC 350cm ³ 3025 ~ 600 UM5AS-
					counts ~ 8 / channel
09:17:45	P1 ↓	FL00 → 260	226	51°6' / 1°24'	696mb -4.5 / -30.5°C 20 m/s / 259°
					PC550 ~ 5
09:20:10	P1	FL20	256	51°0' / 1°36'	-9.2 / -25.7 641mb 24 m/s / 274 deg
09:22:09	P1	FL40	256	51°0' / 1°48'	-14.37 / -20.7 593mb 28 m/s / 259
		FL156			Bumbos - Slight
09:24:12	P1	FL160	258		Cloud - CPI → Core Cloud Partic
					-19.31 / -32.6 543
09:26:00	P1	FL182			500
		FL190			Cloud - 10 particles cm ³

Cloud
96-295

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B**..... Date Name Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:42:43		FL 220	254		2DS gone down - scrubbing white -
09:31:38	P1 and	FL 240	254	50°44'/2°42'	592mb -37.53/-35.26 43m/s/271
					RADSEARSEN - in hand -
					nothing much in level -
09:33:	R1 &	FL 240	02	50°54'/2°36'	-36.1/-37.4 392mb 43m/s/262°
					CPI bullets, plates, aggregates/chunks large
					CPC 400 - other 600
					CVI CPC ~ PCASP ~ 20-30 counts/d
					RADSEARSEN - Overhead
					CB - 6km 5km
					nothing below - w/level CT 1 1/2 - 2 km
09:42:54	R1 and	FL 240	53	51°6'/1°12'	RADSEARSEN - -36.1/-37.65 41m/s/268°
					2DP - no more - turn it off
					RADSEARSEN in hand work
09:47:23					FL - small shear layer - maybe supercooled H ₂ O
09:48:28	R2	FL 220	260	51°6'/1°30'	426mb -32.8/-30.5 41/275
					AMS CPC ~ 200 CVI CPC zero
					Probed Clear Air - W CPC non zero ☺
					Butanal is zero .
					Core Cloud - in/out cloud - check at times
					QI only ice - Big ice
09:57:24	R2	FL 220			RAD SEARSEN
					CB - Ci ~ 4km now
					AMS - not much - CPC ~ 400 in
10:01:02	R2	FL 220			Probed

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.338** Date Name Page **3** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:02:18	R2 end	FL 220	250		-32.8/-31.9, 45 m/s / 267 427 mb
10:09:22	R3 start	FL 200	56	50°54'/1°42'	-29.1/-27.9, 41 m/s / 256 485 mb
					AMS - WCR - 100-200
					CVI But CPC - 1000 - too high in cloud
					Placids in AMS again
					CVI CPC - touching hygrometer - maybe OK
10:14:15	R3 end	FL 200	54	51°6'/1°12'	-27.4/-26.9 42 m/s / 273° 466 mb
					Just got zero on WCR (- in clear air pocket)
					CI CB seen - 4km (full streaks)
10:19:32	R4 start	FL 160	259	51°6'/1°30'	Sunshine to LMS - predicts clear air
					-23.99/-24.82 505 mb 43 / 268 mb
					Ran into clear air 1/2 way through run
~10:30:20	R4				- Switched to Rosemount inlet
10	R4 end				W/L 2 DC
10:37:24	R5 start	FL 160			Will stall in clear air - probably run introduced
					(RADSEAR - warned) at end
10:40:10	R5	FL 160	72	50°54'/2°12'	-18.99/-24.6 548 mb 41 / 263°
10:40:10					RADSEAR :- Ice Full Streaks - base 4km
					True Bar - Sun
10:47:06	R5.2	FL 160	259	51°6'/1°24'	-20.95/-20.75 33 m/s / 58° 548 mb
10:48:55	R5.2	Out of cloud again		51°0'/1°30'	Water CPC ~ 0-3 CVI CPC ~ 131
					Sunshine Inlets → Rose Falls Off
					-20.09/-22.75 36 m/s / 264° 548 mb

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.338** Date 17/01/08 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:58:00		FL160			RADSEARCH - update
					Cl tops 9km
					at 14 km -
11:01:00					CVI zero checks - AMS → UNSAS → CVI
11:02:40	RS.2end	FL160	252	50°48'/2°42'	-18.58/-27.31 39m/s/266 548mb
11:04:37	R6st	FL140	67	50°54'/2°42'	-15.9/-17.52 31m/s/262 593mb
11:14:23	R6	FL140		51°6'/1°24'	Overhead Ch.1 bottom
11:15:52	R6end	FL140	52	51°6'/1°12'	594mb -16.1°/-16.33 26m/s/262°
11:19:05	P2	FL140↑	262	51.6°/1.16'	594mb 25m/s/271° -16.28°/-17.42°
11:19:49	P2				Over head Ch.1 bottom - climbing to FL300
11:20:50	P2				Smoking Filter off - AMS/ UNSAS → CVI
11:24:17		FL 200			
		225			
		250			
		263			
		275			
		300			
		310			
11:35:48	P2end	310			
11:37:33	R7st	FL310	68	50°54'/2°42'	-54.77/-55.62 53m/s/208 286mb
11:41:00					RADSEARCH - in km - updated
11:43:30					Under control - No air conditioning - Photos
11:44:01	R7end	FL310			
					Just in CT on beam and end of Run
11:45:49	R7.2f	FL310	260	51°0'/-54.5'	286mb -55.47/-54.5° 63m/s/274°
					RADsearch updated at pass overhead w beam (turn on light dead)

On track → 13:15

11:15
 Ref 20 mins
 11:35
 150 300 310
 :05 260 290 260
 :20 260 240
 :35 240 210
 :50 220 180
 :05 200 150
 :20 180 120

7 runs

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DigiMemo e-Page

ADPRASE-ICE

Flight No **B.336** Date **17/01/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **S** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					115 kts head wind West bound - just above CT.
11.52:44	R7.2	FL310			1.43 g/kg Turb/Wake - struggling with sample T AMS-CPC ISO cm ⁻³ CPC CPC 350 cm ⁻² as CVI CPC (CVI as Ac unkl) = Water CPC = 40 ← ultra fine → should be A but fine losses? boreal CPC = 65 UHMAS suddenly too. for check at end should occur.
11.59.50	R7.2 end	FL310			CT dropping - no cloud at FL290 - descends further to be in cloud at 27500 - still above Radar cont. clouds should be in cloud at 260
12.03.44	R8 st	FL260			Starting out of cloud - soon into CT Filters off - AMS/UHMAS → CVI CB - 3-4 km - around 4km (13200 ft)
	R8 end	FL260			
12.10.29	R8 end	FL260			in CT - RADIOMETER request water seen - no -44.45 / -42.29 358 mb 40/267°
12:13:46	R9 st	FL240			except FL140
12:16:00					Out of CT again CT dropping quickly
12:15:02	R9	FL240			Observed Chiral bitan - near CT. Out of cloud for some distance
12:18:15	R9				Back into cloud

2 complete cycles

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B338** Date 17/01/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12.27.23	R9	FL240	53	50°48'/2°24'	Above CT 391mb -36.52/-36.14 34/266'
12.31.06					CT = 7½ - 8km Polesw
					Mixed Phase cloud at 74000 km
					ATC maintain ↑ FL200
12.51.53	R9 end	FL240			
12.34.11	R10 st	FL210	61	50°00'/2°30'	-31.05/-33.26 49/265 444 proto
					CT descending all time
12.38.20	R10	FL210			Fillics of - look to be heading into cloud
12:39:21	R10	FL210			→ AMS
					CPI / AMS → AMS CND out
12:41:05	R10	FL210			Right in CT
12.41.59	R10	FL210			Overhead Chublotin
12:43:14	R10 end	FL210	53	51°6'/1°12'	-31.25/-30.82°C 445mb 44mbs/261
12:47:51					
12:48:37	R11	FL180	57	51.6°/1°30'	-23.65/-21.73 43mbs/260 504mb
12.50.40	R11				Cloud thin - can see below and above - outside gate - then into thicker cloud
12.53.02					Above to be embedded by fast jet.
12.56.57	R11				lot more LW in cloud - very
					CPI seeing drops
12 57 →	R11				Out of most cloud - very thin layer
12	R11 end				
13.07.52	R12 st	FL150	53	50°48'/2°42'	570mb -16.49/-22.99 45mbs/255
					Upper Str - Ice below and above
					boxes 4km

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ICE-APPRAISE

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.338** Date **17/01/08** Name **K.N. Bower** Page **7** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:18:21	R12.2	FL150	269	51°6'/1°12'	-17.5/-21.51 41/262 970 mb
13:20:02	R12.2	FL150	263	51°6'/1°24'	Overhead cloud bottom - still cloud free - all cloud (mid/high level) burnt/moved off
					Sized around NO_2 , SO_2 , H_2SO_4 - no visible
Instrument Status Reports					<p>Films better today</p> <p>Water CPC - problem early in - OK after 30 mins</p> <p>↓</p> <p>ZDS - stopped working</p> <p>VHSRS /</p> <p>CPT /</p> <p>AMS same condition</p> <p>PCASP - 210</p> <p>ZDC good</p> <p>ZDP alt early</p> <p>FSSP - short widths - Oil sensor low</p> <p>SID - pouring</p> <p>Turbulence - better today - rel to last flight</p> <p>Total Water - heater not grab near enough to base sample T in tank</p> <p>Chlor Chem - loose pipe ends on - edit later ok</p>
13:38:37	R12.2 end	FL150	255	50°48'/2°30'	571 mb -16.64/-25.39 45m/s/266 Cloud Free
13:41:46	R13.4 end	FL120	81	50°54'/2°30'	642 mb -12.63/-20.5 36m/s/257 Clear
					- Cloud above to South of us - Clear ahead/N
					- Cloud below - CT ~ 6000 ft
13:49:45	R13.4 end	FL120			
14:09:48	Trans	FL100 end			<p>Just last TW on Nev3 - through last bit of cloud. Trans off FL100 was in cloud w -4°C</p>

KNB

14:22:27 Land

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 338

Date: 17/01/08	Operator:KT/PDR	DRS Time:07:41	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
																Sid2 not fitted	
																Cip not fitted	
																Instruments on post security	
																Heaters on post take-off	
8:53:35	13	0.48	129	4000		2030	250	766	200							FL100	
8:57:00	20	0.54	220	1000		236	150	1700	200							PCASP VREF=8.4V	
08:59:00	6	0.12	224	0		0		NOISE								2DP HEATERS SWITCHED ON. D'OH!!	
09:05:00	8	0.09	225	0		0		NOISE								SLIGHT ICING ON CANISTERS	
09:10:00	3	0.10	225	0		0		0									
09:15:00	5	0.08	225	0		0		0									
09:17:52	6	0.18	225	0		0		0								START P1 FL100	
09:18:59	3	0.08	225	0		0		0								FL110	
09:20:05	3	0.08	225	0		0		0								FL120	
09:21:10	5	0.08	225	0		0		0								FL130	
09:22:06	6	0.08	225	0		0		0								FL140	
09:23:10	9	0.08	225	0		0		0								FL150	
09:24:00	23	0.08	226	100		65	675	2000	800							FL160	
09:25:00	5	0.09	227	0		0		0								FL170	
09:26:00	6	0.14	227	80		3	350	2500	1200							FL180	
09:27:00	144	0.37	228	200		57	550	2700	1200							FL190	
09:28:00	900	0.49	238	900		195	750	30000	1200							FL200	
09:29:00	77	0.47	284	300		92	475	20783	1200							FL210	
09:30:00	122	0.41	300	300		51	425	6000	800							FL220	
09:31:38	104	0.35	213	400		130	600	23183	600						8,11	FL240 END P1	
09:34:00	42	0.38	330	500		192	375	20700	375						11	START R1 FL240	
09:36:00	9	0.48	353	400		230	550	NOISE							11		
09:38:00	10	0.11	376	10		75	450	NOISE							4		
09:40:00	114	0.36	424	50		122	425	NOISE							8		
09:42:00	167	0.47	453	1000		147	525	NOISE							8		
09:42:54	41	0.5	471	800		69	300	NOISE							8	END R1	
09:45:00	14	0.3	489	1000		206	525	NOISE							8		
09:47:00	4	0.07	523	10		1	400	OFF							8	2DP SWITCHED OFF AFTER CONSULT	
09:48:29	9	0.1	524	1		0	0									START R2	
09:51:00	20	0.26	527	1000		114	600										
09:53:00	5	0.08	534	80		2	350								4	FL220	
09:55:00	452	0.36	539	800		168	675								8,11		
09:57:00	8	0.15	559	800		135	575								4		
09:59:00	11	0.32	588	200		62	625								8		
10:01:00	6	0.32	605	20		14	500								4,8		
10:02:20	154	0.5	637	900		77	375								8	END R2	
10:04:00	69	0.42	648	100		150	625								8	START R3 FL200	
10:06:00	8	0.5	667	100		60	800								4,8		
10:08:00	206	0.45	698	800		123	700								4,8		

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =1.1		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	Not fitted	Not fitted

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 338

Date: 17/01/08	Operator:KT/PDR	DRS Time:07:41	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:10:00	11	0.2	722	400		15	450								8		
10:12:00	11	0.5	732	100		33	775								8		
10:14:00	53	0.27	744	400		64	525								8		
10:14:15	19	0.32	746	800		133	800								8	END R3 FL200	
10:16:00	8	0.41	756	300		102	775								8		
10:18:00	21	0.36	781	300		94	450								8		
10:18:50	233	0.40	793	200		40	725									FL190	
10:19:38	14	0.23	795	20		9	500								8	FL180 START R4	
10:22:00	7	0.25	810	10		9	400								8		
10:24:00	17	0.33	819	200		64	575								8		
10:26:00	56	0.44	857	800		98	750								8		
10:28:00	3	0.16	864	30		5	400								8		
10:30:00	7	0.08	869	0		0											
10:32:00	10	0.07	872	0		0											
10:34:00	3	0.07	872	10		3	300								8		
10:35:13	7	0.10	873	80		42	550								8	End r4 FL180	
10:36:15	8	0.07	874	30		28	375								8	FL170	
10:37:28	6	0.09	875	2		0										FL160 START R5	
10:40:00	7	0.1	875	0		0											
10:42:00	8	.1	875	5		0											
10:44:00	18	0.37	877	100		5	200								4,8		
10:45:38	20	0.31	881	100		18	775								8	END R5.1 FL160	
10:47:06	3	0.18	884	10		10	600								8	START R5.2 FL160	
10:49:00	9	0.08	892	0		0											
10:51:00	25	0.3	894	10		4.5	425										
10:53:00	8	0.03	896	0		0											
10:55:00	11	0.07	904	2		1.5	600								8		
10:57:00	4	0.09	906	1		0											
10:59:00	6	0.1	906	0		0											
11:01:00	5	0.11	9-06	1		0											
11:02:42	7	0.15	906	0		0										END R5.2 FL160	
11:04:00	11	0.09	906	0		0										START R6 FL140	
11:06:30	13	0.11	906	0		0											
11:08:00	6	0.09	906	0		0											
11:10:00	8	0.09	906	0		0											
11:12:00	9.6	0.08	907	10		6	400								8		
11:14:00	6	0.08	907	1		0											
11:16:00	8	0.08	907	10		3.5	500								8	END R6 FL140	
11:18:00	10	0.11	908	3		1	500										
11:19:10	5	0.11	908	3		2.5	400								0	START P2 FL140	
11:20:15	4																
		0.2	909	10		34	450								8	FL150	
11:21:12	34	0.32	919	130		60	800								8	FL160	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =1.1		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	Not fitted	Not fitted

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 338

Date: 17/01/08	Operator:KT/PDR	DRS Time:07:41	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:22:05	7	0.3	931	100		17	325								8,4	FL170	
11:23:34	440	0.47	943	1000		47	550								8	FL190	
11:24:20	17	0.07	947	200		62	725								8	FL200	
11:55:10	1.4	0.07	949	0		0										FL210	
11:26:00	3	0.08	949	100		105	325								8,11	FL220	
11:27:00	10	0.25	956	900		154	400								8	FL230	
11:27:55	55	0.44	973	800		530	675								8,11	FL240	
11:29:00	17	0.5	1012	1000		267	200								11,8	FL250	
11:30:04	11	0.48	1078	1000		102	100								11	FL260	
11:31:00	0		1086	0		0										FL270	
11:31:55	4.5	0.5	1089	200		165	175								11	FL280	
11:33:00	7	0.6	1115	200		111	125								11	FL290	
11:34:07	0	0.1	1123	0		0										FL300	
11:35:48	4	0.14	1123	0		0										END P2 FL310	
11:37:34	2	0.06	1208	0		0										SRART R7 FL 310	
11:40:00	3	0.08	1208	0		0											
11:44:00	3	0.3	1213	100		93	150								11	END R7 FL310	
11:45:52	1.5	0.3	1220	0		0										START R7.2 FL310 (ABOVE CLOUD)	
11:48:00	0.7	0.1	1220	0		0											
11:50:00	0.7	0.6	1220	0		0											
11:58:00	0.7	0.12	1220	0		0											
11:59:48	0	0.08	1220	0		0										END R7.2 FL310	
12:00:42	2	0.07	1220	0		0										FL300	
12:01:18	1	0.12	1220	0		0										FL290	
12:02:34	10	0.44	1221	200		100	150								11	FL280	
12:03:41	7	0.45	1221	200		180	125								11	FL260 START R8.1	
12:05:00	7	0.47	1229	800		127	175								11		
12:07:00	2	0.07	1231	200		20	100								11		
12:09:00	5	0.16	1240	200		65	125								11		
12:10:24	4	0.31	1244	400		47	225								11	END RUN 8	
12:13:00	22	0.29	1292	300		67	175								11		
12:13:46	11	0.40	1302	80		14	250								11	START RUN FL240	
12:16:00	3	0.09	1328	1		0											
12:18:00	0.7	0.12	1329	0		0											
12:19:00	7	0.22	1331	80		70	250								8,11		
12:21:00	15	0.40	1366	800		284	225								8,11		
12:23:00	24	0.52	1448	900		480	250								8,11		
12:25:00	17	0.46	1502	900		400	225								8,11		
12:27:00	1	0.08	1532	8		1	175								8,11		
12:29:00	3	0.05	1532	0		0											
12:31:00	3	0.06	1532	0		0											
12:31:54	0	0	1532	0		0										END RUN 9	
12:32:33	2	0.08	1532	0		0										FL230	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =1.1		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	Not fitted	Not fitted

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 338

Date: 17/01/08	Operator:KT/PDR	DRS Time:07:41	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 4 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:33:31	3	0.08	1533	100		100	300								8	FL220	
12:34:13	5	0.08	1533	0		0										FL210 START RUN 10	
12:36:00	3	.11	1533	0		0											
12:38:00	3	0.08	1544	20		6.5	300								4		
12:40:00	6	0.09	1547	100		93	450								4,11		
12:42:00	21	0.34	1554	100		113	175								8		
12:43:15	9	0.02	1562	100		60	225								8	END RUN 10 FL210	
12:46:30	10	0.23	1648	100		53	250								4,11		
12:47:55	12	0.29	1672	100		75	300									FL 190	
12:48:39	25	0.3	2027	100		41	675								8	START RUN 11 FL 180	
12:51:00	14	0.07	2657	2		0											
12:53:00	11	0.08	2682	1000		0.5	600								8,4		
12:55:00	11	0.09	2877	100		6	200								8,4		
12:57:00	14	0.5	2877	1000		6	300								1,8		
12:59:00	7	0.08	2877	0		0											
13:01:30	4.4	0.07				0										FFSSP1 RESTARTED	
13:05:48	6	0.08				0										END RUN 11	
13:07:54	6	0.08	0	0		0										START RUN12 FL150	
13:10:00	8	0.09	0	0		0											
13:15:00	9	0.08	0	0		0											
13:16:59	11	0.08	0	0		0										END R12 FL150	
13:18:22	7	0.08	0	0		0											
13:23:00	8	0.08	1	0		0											
13:26:00	7	0.07	39	0		0											
13:29:00	13	0.08	57	0		0											
13:32:00	10	0.07	57	0		0											
13:40:00	10	0.08	57	0		0										END R12	
13:41:06	9	0.07	63	0		0										FL130	
13:41:48	17	0.1	63	1		0										START R13 FL120	
13:46:00	12	0.07	63	0		0											
13:49:00	7	0.08	63	0		0											
13:49:45	4	0.1	63	0		0										End r13	
13:56:00	15	0.08	64	0		0											
13:58:00	14	0.14	65	100		400	750								4		
14:00:00	158	0.51	159	1000		400	725								2		
14:02:00	405	0.46	692	1000		1069	800								2		
14:04:00	157	0.45	1107	200		125	775								2		
14:06:00	26	0.27	1107	700		43	625								2		
14:08:00	176	0.53	1107	1000		>500	600								2		
14:10:00	22	0.2	1107	100		88	575								2		
14:12:00	69	0.1	1107	100		9	700								5/6		

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =1.1		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	Not fitted	Not fitted

CVI log

1/17/08 8:27:26 AM
1/17/08 8:29:05 AM start up ok, pcasp ok, cpc ok, flows ok,
1/17/08 8:30:07 AM lyman zero cwc problems??
1/17/08 8:31:01 AM zero lyman on full dilution???
1/17/08 8:53:33 AM lower counterf flow to 3.6
1/17/08 8:53:39 AM lower counterf flow to 3.6
1/17/08 8:57:22 AM remember to check up on cvi-horace comms. B337 - horace returning
message 'unable to send to cvi'
1/17/08 8:58:04 AM heater controls all ok, Tsample returning 16.8deg
1/17/08 9:00:19 AM 3.6 is good zeroo for just cvi
1/17/08 9:01:47 AM SLR with aerosol for cal of counterflow
1/17/08 9:03:19 AM SLR with aerosol for cal of counterflow
1/17/08 9:06:03 AM counterflow still zero's at 3.2 so add 0.3 to set counterflow at
3.5
1/17/08 9:06:09 AM counterflow still zero's at 3.2 so add 0.3 to set counterflow at
3.5
1/17/08 9:09:29 AM ice present on tip
1/17/08 9:14:06 AM switch to aerosol to get some hygro data to compare with twc
1/17/08 9:15:01 AM delay time for cvi? readings increase about 20seconds after
turning pressure pump off
1/17/08 9:15:13 AM flying in clear air
1/17/08 9:17:33 AM turning, soon to be climbing
1/17/08 9:17:57 AM profile 1#
1/17/08 9:17:58 AM profile 1#
1/17/08 9:21:37 AM lyman looks to have goo dvisual agreement with TWC probe
1/17/08 9:24:16 AM inu pitch =7.5 cf 7.0
1/17/08 9:24:34 AM fisco has slow response time to urbukent "bumps"
1/17/08 9:25:51 AM 7.75 INU 7.6 FISCO
1/17/08 9:26:22 AM 7.75 INU 7.6 FISCO
1/17/08 9:26:32 AM 7.75 INU 7.6 FISCO
1/17/08 9:27:21 AM PRESSURE PUMP BACK ON
1/17/08 9:29:22 AM PRESSURE PUMP BACK ON
1/17/08 9:29:49 AM AEROSOL TO CVI
1/17/08 9:31:49 AM RUN
1/17/08 9:34:08 AM RUN 1 NOW FL240
1/17/08 9:34:45 AM TURN TIP HEATER UP TO TRY AND REDUCE ICE ON TIP
1/17/08 9:35:04 AM TIP TO 35
1/17/08 9:36:12 AM TIP TO 35
1/17/08 9:36:18 AM TIP TO 35
1/17/08 9:43:00 AM RUN END
1/17/08 9:43:23 AM LYMAN CVI CWC SEEMS MUCH HIGHER THAN TWC IN ICE CLOUD
1/17/08 9:44:44 AM LYMAN CVI CWC SEEMS MUCH HIGHER THAN TWC IN ICE CLOUD
1/17/08 9:44:50 AM LYMAN CVI CWC SEEMS MUCH HIGHER THAN TWC IN ICE CLOUD
1/17/08 9:45:25 AM TIP UP TO 38 DEG
1/17/08 9:45:38 AM NO SIGN OF ORGANICS FROM AMS YET
1/17/08 9:47:53 AM FLOW SAMPLE TEMP IS LOW, t SAMPLE STILL READING 21
1/17/08 9:48:07 AM ICE ON TIP
1/17/08 9:48:32 AM RUN WEST FL220
1/17/08 9:49:13 AM OUT OF CLOUD
1/17/08 9:57:27 AM TIP TO 40, SAMPLE STILL UNDERHEATING, T SAMPLE STILL OK AT 22.2
1/17/08 10:01:32 AM STILL ICE ON TIP
1/17/08 10:04:29 AM START RUN
1/17/08 10:06:20 AM POSSIBLE ORGANICS AMS SIGNATURE? TIP DOWN TO 37#
1/17/08 10:10:21 AM Still some organics? drop tip again to 35
1/17/08 10:12:56 AM Still some organics? drop tip again to 35
1/17/08 10:13:11 AM Still some organics? drop tip again to 35
1/17/08 10:14:14 AM 10:08 to 10:13 very good similarity in trace between nevz and
lyman cvi#
1/17/08 10:14:20 AM end run
1/17/08 10:19:48 AM run4 fl180
1/17/08 10:37:36 AM run 5 fl160 east
1/17/08 10:38:20 AM out of cloud
1/17/08 10:44:13 AM fallstreaks showing up??? flying below true cloud base
1/17/08 10:45:41 AM end run
1/17/08 10:47:08 AM run west
1/17/08 10:47:14 AM run west fl160
1/17/08 10:49:20 AM aerosol racks back to rosemount

1/17/08 10:49:55 AM lyman reading 0.17 maybe sohuld be closer to zero at this point?
1/17/08 11:00:57 AM zero check
1/17/08 11:01:00 AM zero check
1/17/08 11:01:22 AM zero set l control to 3.0 leave to allow for lag
1/17/08 11:01:56 AM zero set l control to 3.0 leave to allow for lag
1/17/08 11:02:04 AM zero set l control to 2.6 leave to allow for lag
1/17/08 11:02:36 AM zero set l control to 2.6 leave to allow for lag
1/17/08 11:02:53 AM zero set l control to 2.6 leave to allow for lag
1/17/08 11:03:08 AM zufsas seeing particles at l=2.6
1/17/08 11:03:20 AM revert back to l=3.0+0.3
1/17/08 11:03:52 AM revert back to l=3.0+0.3
1/17/08 11:04:01 AM revert back to l=3.0+0.3
1/17/08 11:04:20 AM set L to 2.8 check for zero on UFSAS
1/17/08 11:05:16 AM set L to 2.8 check for zero on UFSAS
1/17/08 11:05:28 AM 2.8 is good, set l to 3.1 and leave
1/17/08 11:05:53 AM 2.8 is good, set l to 3.1 and leave
1/17/08 11:15:58 AM runend
1/17/08 11:18:29 AM turning - high bank angle, PCASP channel 2 is near zero -
indicating that it might actually be seeing something real
1/17/08 11:22:19 AM tip icing
1/17/08 11:22:31 AM cpc temp flashing
1/17/08 11:37:15 AM going to aerosol
1/17/08 11:37:35 AM run fl310
1/17/08 11:38:26 AM increase opc sample flow
1/17/08 11:38:59 AM increase opc sample flow
1/17/08 11:52:38 AM 1.43 g/kg
1/17/08 11:53:02 AM twc below limits of temp
1/17/08 11:55:57 AM water cpc running off cvi inlet, cvi in aerosol time for
comparison
1/17/08 11:57:11 AM uhsas going to cvi
1/17/08 12:00:44 PM going back to counterflow
1/17/08 12:03:43 PM run at fl260 cloud ytop
1/17/08 12:05:33 PM reduce pcasp flow
1/17/08 12:05:43 PM cwc showing patchy cloud
1/17/08 12:34:17 PM inbound start
1/17/08 12:34:23 PM reduced pcasp sample flow
1/17/08 12:40:58 PM run in cloud top
1/17/08 12:48:40 PM fl 180 in cloud run srart
1/17/08 12:56:01 PM pass through cloud patch, cvi tip gets more ice deposited during
passages, this time around the bottom half only - flow angle cf pcasp
1/17/08 1:06:49 PM harrier fly past!
1/17/08 1:25:29 PM into aerosol mode
1/17/08 1:40:54 PM descending to fl120
1/17/08 1:41:43 PM last run fl120, into chilbolton#
1/17/08 1:50:20 PM e3nd of run now on transit back
1/17/08 1:50:39 PM will set ams on cvi inlet for transit back
1/17/08 1:51:40 PM ams on cvi inlet
1/17/08 1:52:35 PM Wcpc about 200 less
1/17/08 1:55:49 PM aerosol racks back to roseount
1/17/08 1:56:47 PM increase tip heater to 50deg
1/17/08 1:57:00 PM will run aerosl racks of cvi at 14:00
1/17/08 1:58:59 PM aerosol racsk back to cvi
1/17/08 1:59:30 PM in cloud watching cwc closly not above 12 yet
1/17/08 1:59:44 PM in cloud watching cwc closly not above 12 yet
1/17/08 1:59:51 PM in cloud watching cwc closly not above 12 yet
1/17/08 2:00:43 PM in cloud watching cwc closly not above 12 yet
1/17/08 2:29:57 PM laanded shut down and restart for lyman zero
1/17/08 2:32:03 PM vacuum pump and counter flow switched off
1/17/08 2:34:01 PM pumps back on filtered cabin air now being sent to lyman
1/17/08 2:34:11 PM wait for stabalisation then zero
1/17/08 2:34:57 PM wait for stabalisation then zero
1/17/08 2:35:19 PM lyman zesro'd
1/17/08 2:35:32 PM shut down, and getr data off

Flight:

B338

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:	Not Fitted
Heimann:	OK
Deiced Temp:	OK
Non-deiced Temp:	OK

Hygrometers

FWVS:	Minor Problems
General Eastern:	OK
Johnson Williams:	OK
Nevezorov:	Minor Problems
Total Water Probe:	Minor Problems

Cameras

Downward Facing:	Fitted, Not Operated
Forward Facing:	OK
Rearward Facing:	Fitted, Not Operated
Upward Facing:	OK

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:	Fitted, Not Operated
GIN Applanix:	OK
INU Honeywell:	OK
Radar Altimeter:	OK
RVSM IAS:	OK
RVSM Static Pressure:	OK
XR5 GPS:	OK

Report Created 06/02/2008
15:38:13

Misc Core

AMTG:	OK
AVAPS:	Fitted, Not Operated
Cabin Pressure:	OK
Fax machine:	Fitted, Not Operated
Printer:	OK
S9 Static Pressure:	OK
Satcom C:	OK
Satcom H:	OK
Turb Centre-Static:	OK
Turb Left Right:	OK
Turb Up-Down:	OK
Turb Horizontal Chk:	OK
Turb Vertical Chk:	Minor Problems
Weather Radar:	Fitted, Not Operated

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:	OK
DLU BBR Lower:	OK
DLU BBR Upper:	OK
DLU Core Chem:	OK
DLU Core Consoles:	OK
DLU Port Aft:	Minor Problems
DLU Port Fwd:	Not Fitted
DLU Stbd Fwd:	Not Fitted

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:	OK
BBR (IR) Lower:	Minor Problems
BBR (red) Lower:	OK

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:	Minor Problems
BBR (IR) Upper:	OK
BBR (red) Upper:	Minor Problems

ARIES:	Fitted, Not Operated
DEIMOS:	Fitted, Not Operated
IR Camera:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Lower:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Upper:	Not Fitted
JO1D Lower:	Not Fitted
JO1D Upper:	Not Fitted
MARSS:	Fitted, Not Operated
SHIMS Lower:	Not Fitted
SHIMS Upper:	Not Fitted
SWS:	Not Fitted
TAFTS:	Not Fitted

Last Updated:

17/01/2008 15:52:42

Cloud Probes

2DC:	OK
2DP:	Minor Problems
FFSSP:	Minor Problems
PCASP:	Minor Problems
2DS:	Duff Data
ADA:	Not Fitted
CAPS:	Not Fitted
CCN:	Not Fitted
CDP:	Not Fitted
CIP 100:	Not Fitted
CIP 25:	Not Fitted
CPI:	OK
CVI:	OK
SID1:	OK
SID2:	Not Fitted

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:	OK
Filters 47mm:	OK
Filters 90mm:	Not Fitted
Neph - Dry:	OK
Neph - Wet:	Fitted, Not Operated
PSAP:	Fitted, Not Operated
AMS:	Minor Problems
CPC 3025 (AMS):	Minor Problems
INC:	Not Fitted
VACC:	Not Fitted
CPC 3010A (CVI):	OK

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:	OK
NOx TE42C:	OK
Ozone TE49C:	OK
Ozone TE49:	Not Fitted
SO2 TE43C:	Fitted, Not Operated
TDLAS (NIR) CH4:	OK
TDLAS (NIR) CO2:	OK
FAGE:	Not Fitted
Formaldehyde:	Not Fitted
NOx FAAM:	Not Fitted
NOxy:	Not Fitted
ORAC:	Not Fitted
PAN:	Fitted, Not Operated
PERCA:	Not Fitted
Peroxide:	Not Fitted
PTRMS:	Not Fitted
TDLAS (1C):	Not Fitted
WAS Bags:	Not Fitted
WAS Bottles:	Not Fitted

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:	Not Fitted
LIDAR:	Not Fitted
LTI:	Fitted, Not Operated
SAW Hygrometer:	Fitted, Not Operated

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B338

Date: 17 January 2008

Instruments

1. CGPS – PC u/s
2. Weather Radar – No Wx Radar software on pc
3. Aft console inboard pc u/s
4. IIU – Wouldn't go into GC Align on pre-flight. Tried re-setting power and HORACE process, no good. Noticed IIU hadn't responded to DLU start-up even though showing "Sending Packets" on DLU menu page Option 6. On Option 7, showing T4 messages counting up, not T1. Reset IIU CB then okay.
5. PAFT DLU – Exactly same as IIU problem. Reset PAFT DLU CB then okay.
6. Filters – Cabin air leaking into Upper Filter holder pre-flight (i.e. audible). Tightened up back by turning holder then okay.
7. Upper BBRs – Red signal on HORACE higher than Clear
8. Lower BBRs – Pyrgeometer has occasional dropouts
9. 2DS – Went down at 0920 during Profile climb, TAT = -33deg C
10. 2DP – Switch off at 0947, not working,
11. PCASP – very low counts
12. Turb Probe – may be some icing on AOA Diff channel, otherwise okay.
13. AMS CPC – Possible leak
14. TWC – Status light on at FL310, TAT = -53C, Status Bit = 4091DRSU, TSAM = 571DRSU.
15. Nevzorov TWC – Alarm light flashing on transit return to Cranfield in precip cloud, TAT – 10C. Suspect TWC sensor u/s.

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

1 x connect to check for emails – nil uploaded

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 17 Jan 2008 Flight No: B 338 Pre-Flighter: BW

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	<u>Missed INU</u>
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	<u>See DLU above</u>
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	<u>M6</u>
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		ICEX applied		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B338:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	14 Mar 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras

4 x Upward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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